

SYSTEMATIC COUNTING OF RESTRICTED PARTITIONS

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Abstract

We use ‘partial difference operator schemes’ and dynamical programming to design algorithms that systematically count sets of integer partitions avoiding *any* set of patterns (of a certain, natural, kind). We describe two approaches, a ‘negative’ (adapting the Goulden–Jackson algorithm for enumerating words), and a ‘positive’ approach that turns out to be much more efficient. Nevertheless, the negative approach has theoretical interest.

1. Introduction

One of the cornerstones of enumerative combinatorics (and number theory!) is the topic of (integer) partitions. Recall that a partition of a non-negative integer n is a list of integers $(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k)$ such that $\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_k \geq 1$ and $\lambda_1 + \dots + \lambda_k = n$.

As usual, we will denote the number of integer partitions of n by $p(n)$. This is a very famous sequence, OEIS sequence A41.

While there is no easy, direct formula for $p(n)$, there is a nice generating function that goes back to Leonhard Euler. Denoting the number of integer partitions of n by $p(n)$, Euler discovered that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n) q^n = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^i}.$$

The ‘bible’ of the theory of partitions is George Andrews’ classic [1]. We also strongly recommend Drew Sills’ fascinating monograph [9].

Suppose that we did not know about Euler’s generating function, and we were given the task of computing the first, say, 1000 terms of the sequence $p(n)$; how

would we proceed? The most straightforward way would be to try and use dynamical programming. Note that partitions have the *hereditary* property. If we chop-off the largest entry of the partition of n , $(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k)$, we would get a shorter partition, $(\lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k)$, of $n - \lambda_1$. Because of the condition $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2$, we have to ‘remember’ what λ_1 was, after kicking it out. So we are forced to consider a more general quantity, let us call it $P(n, m)$, enumerating the set of partitions of n whose largest part is exactly m . Once we can compute this more general quantity, the original object of interest, $p(n)$, is given by

$$p(n) = \sum_{m=1}^n P(n, m).$$

In order to compute $P(n, m)$, we have the obvious recurrence (or partial difference equation)

$$P(n, m) = \sum_{m'=1}^m P(n - m, m'), \quad n \geq m \geq 1, \quad (\textit{FundamentalRecurrence})$$

subject to the boundary conditions $P(m, m) = 1$ and $P(n, m) = 0$ if $n < m$. Replacing n by $n - 1$ and m by $m - 1$ in the above recurrence, and subtracting, one gets the even simpler recurrence

$$P(n, m) = P(n - 1, m - 1) + P(n - m, m). \quad (\textit{SimplifiedFundamentalRecurrence})$$

This gives a quadratic time (and quadratic memory) algorithm, $O(N^2)$ for compiling a table of $p(n)$ for $1 \leq n \leq N$.

This is not the most efficient way to compile such a table. An even better way is via Euler’s recurrence (e.g., [1], p. 12)

$$p(n) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{j-1} (p(n - j(3j - 1)/2) + p(n - j(3j + 1)/2)),$$

that was famously used by Major Percy MacMahon to compile such a table, that led to Ramanujan’s discovery of his famous congruences (see [1]).

Already Euler considered the enumeration of sets of partitions obeying some restrictions. For example, the set of partitions into distinct parts, let us call it $d(n)$, is given by the generating function ([1], p. 5)

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} d(n)q^n = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 + q^i) = \prod_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^{2i+1}}.$$

More recently, Rogers and Ramanujan independently discovered what we would later call the Rogers–Ramanujan identities, which turned out to have very nice partition theoretic interpretations (these interpretations were discovered independently by MacMahon and Schur; see [9], p.74-77).

The partition theoretic interpretation for the first Rogers–Ramanujan identity has to do with enumerating partitions with the property that the difference between consecutive parts is at least 2, i.e., for which

$$\lambda_i - \lambda_{i+1} \geq 2.$$

The first Rogers–Ramanujan identity states that these numbers, let us call them $d_2(n)$, also have a nice product generating function

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} d_2(n)q^n = \prod_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^{5i+1})(1 - q^{5i+4})}.$$

We can say that distinct partitions *avoid* the ‘pattern’ $[a, a]$ and Rogers–Ramanujan partitions avoid both the pattern $[a, a]$ and the pattern $[a, a - 1]$.

This naturally leads to the question of enumerating partitions avoiding an *arbitrary* (finite) set of patterns, but first let us formally define the notion of a ‘pattern’ in the context of partitions. Note that a commonly used term for our ‘pattern’ is ‘difference condition’ (see the introduction of Nandi’s Ph.D. thesis [7]; also note that Nandi’s conjectures have recently been proved [10]). They are equivalent in our setting, but we choose ‘pattern’ for simplicity.

Definition. A *partition-pattern* is a list $a = [a_1, \dots, a_r]$ of length $r \geq 1$ of non-negative integers.

Definition. A partition $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k)$ *contains* the pattern $a = [a_1, \dots, a_r]$ if there exists $1 \leq i \leq k - r$ such that

$$\lambda_i - \lambda_{i+1} = a_1, \lambda_{i+1} - \lambda_{i+2} = a_2, \dots, \lambda_{i+r-1} - \lambda_{i+r} = a_r.$$

For example, the partition $(7, 6, 5, 4, 4)$ contains the pattern $[1]$ (several times), the pattern $[0]$ (since $4 - 4 = 0$), the pattern $[1, 1]$ (because of 765 and 654), the pattern $[1, 0]$ (because of 544), the pattern $[1, 1, 1]$ (because of 7654), the pattern $[1, 1, 0]$ (because of 6544), and the pattern $[1, 1, 1, 0]$.

Definition. A partition λ *avoids* the pattern a if it does not contain the pattern a .

Definition. A partition λ *avoids* the set of patterns A , if it avoids every pattern in A .

With this language, the class of distinct partitions are those that avoid the pattern $[0]$, while the class of partitions whose differences are at least 2 avoids the set of patterns $\{[0], [1]\}$.

Our goal is to devise an efficient algorithm that inputs an *arbitrary* set of patterns, P , and an arbitrary positive integer N , and outputs the first N terms of the sequence enumerating partitions of n avoiding the set of patterns P .

A natural approach is to adapt the celebrated Goulden–Jackson [3] method to this new context. Since it is based on *sieving* (i.e., ‘signed-counting’ using the deep identity $1 + (-1) = 0$) we call it a *negative* approach.

The Goulden–Jackson method is lucidly explained (and significantly extended) in the article [8]. Recently it has been adapted [2] to counting *compositions* avoiding patterns (of a different kind).

As it turned out, while this ‘negative’ approach is very elegant, and of considerable theoretical interest, it is less efficient than a more straightforward, ‘positive’ approach, to be described later. In addition to its theoretical value, the ‘negative’ approach also serves as a good way to check the correctness of the far more efficient positive approach, in addition to using the ‘brute force’ of mere counting. Since computer programs are still written by very unreliable human beings, it is always good to have numerous checks, by making sure that the outputs to the same problem are always the same, using several approaches, thereby empirically confirming all of them.

2. The ‘Negative’ Approach

Recall that in the Goulden–Jackson Cluster method [3, 8], one finds the weight enumerator for ‘marked words’ and that turns out to be exactly the same as the target weight enumerator, that is, the weight enumerator for words avoiding a given set of subwords. Since the cluster method involves the signed counting of a larger set, and often involves negative numbers, we call it the ‘negative’ approach here. However, in the setting of partitions, we cannot directly use the Goulden–Jackson Cluster method for the following reason:

In the Goulden–Jackson cluster method, one uses the important fact that if one peels off the first letter, or cluster, of a (non-empty) marked word, then the result can be any marked word. So we have the following:

$$M = \{\text{empty_word}\} \cup V M \cup C M.$$

(Note: M is the set of all marked words, V is the alphabet, C is the set of all clusters.)

Our basic idea is the same as in the Goulden–Jackson cluster method (we may call it the cluster method for simplicity from now on). However, since we are working with partitions, not words, we need the parts of the partition to be in non-increasing order. Therefore, when we peel off the first letter or cluster of a (non-empty) marked partition, the result is not any marked partition, but a marked partition with possibly a smaller first part such that after adding the cluster or the letter (that we peeled off) in front, it would still be a partition.

We also define weight a little differently than in the cluster method. Recall that

in the cluster method, $weight(w, S) = (-1)^{|S|} s^{length(w)}$ (S is the set of marks this word has). Here we define $weight(p, S) = (-1)^{|S|} s^{sum(p)}$ (where $sum(p)$ denotes the sum of the parts of p , that is, the integer that p is partitioning).

In order to use dynamical programming, we define the following:

- $P(A, k, m)$: the set of marked partitions that start with k and having m parts, A being the set of patterns to avoid
- $C(A, k, l, w)$: the set of clusters starting with k , ending with l and of width w , A being the set of patterns to avoid
- $w(P(A, k, m))$: the weight enumerator of $P(A, k, m)$
- $w(C(A, k, l, w))$: the weight enumerator of $C(A, k, l, w)$.

Let us start with a marked partition of largest part k and m parts. If the partition is empty ($m = 0$), then the weight enumerator is 1. If $m = 1$, then the weight enumerator is q^k . If $m \geq 2$, the first part of the marked partition can be either part of a cluster or not, so for a fixed set of forbidden patterns A , we have the following decomposition:

$$P = kP \cup CP'.$$

(P is the set of all marked partitions that start with k , having m parts; C is the set of all clusters starting with k , with width no greater than m ; P' is the set of marked partitions whose first part is no greater than the last part of clusters in C .) More precisely, for $m \geq 2$, we have:

$$w(P(A, k, m)) = q^k \sum_{r=1}^k w(P(A, r, m-1)) + \sum_{l=1}^k \sum_{w=1}^m (w(C(A, k, l, w)) \sum_{r=1}^l w(P(A, r, m-w))).$$

It remains to find $w(C(A, k, l, w))$. In order to do this, we introduce $w(C(A, v, k, l, w))$: the weight enumerator for clusters starting with k , with v ($v \in A$) being the first pattern, ending with l and of width w , A being the set of patterns to avoid. For example, if $A = \{[2, 1], [1, 1]\}$, consider the cluster $\{8, 6, 5, 3, 2, 1, \{[8, 6, 5], [5, 3, 2], [3, 2, 1]\}\}$. In this case, v would be $[2, 1]$ (corresponding to the first mark $[8, 6, 5]$). It is apparent that $w(C(A, k, l, w)) = \sum_{v \in A} w(C(A, v, k, l, w))$. How do we find $w(C(A, v, k, l, w))$? For a given cluster, we have two scenarios:

(S1) if the cluster has only one mark, then the weight for the cluster will just be $(-1) \cdot q^{sum(s)}$ (s being the underlying partition). For example, the cluster $\{3, 2, 1, \{[3, 2, 1]\}\}$ has weight $-q^6$;

(S2) if the cluster has more than one mark, we can peel off the first mark (leaving the overlapping part), and we get a smaller cluster. For example, for the cluster $\{8, 6, 5, 3, 2, 1, \{[8, 6, 5], [5, 3, 2], [3, 2, 1]\}\}$, after peeling off the first mark, we are

left with the cluster $\{5, 3, 2, 1, \{[5, 3, 2], [3, 2, 1]\}\}$. So, $weight(\{8, 6, 5, 3, 2, 1, \{[8, 6, 5], [5, 3, 2], [3, 2, 1]\}\}) = -q^{14}weight(\{5, 3, 2, 1, \{[5, 3, 2], [3, 2, 1]\}\})$.

This is done in similar fashion as in the Goulden–Jackson cluster method. However, because of the nature of our extension, the details are more complicated. The first scenario occurs only if our input has width exactly 1 greater than the length of v , and the smallest part to ‘match’ k (the largest part) and the forbidden pattern, that is, $k = l + sum(v)$. To compute the weight for clusters in the second scenario, we first define *OVERLAP*, which takes two partitions u and v and outputs a set of lists. Each list is in the form $[q^i, j]$, where j denotes the number of parts that u and v are overlapping, and i denotes the sum of the parts of u that is not overlapping with v . For example, *OVERLAP*($[4, 3, 2, 2], [2, 2, 2, 1]$) would return $\{[q^7, 2], [q^9, 1]\}$ because there are two possible ways of overlapping here. (Note: ‘overlapping’ is defined in the usual sense, as in the cluster method. Here the two possible overlaps are $[2, 2]$ and $[2]$, the power 7 comes from $4 + 3$, and the power 9 comes from $4 + 3 + 2$.)

Now, since we are really working with patterns (the v in the input for $C(A, v, k, l, w)$ is a pattern, not a partition), we define *OVERLAP1* which takes two patterns u and v and two integers $k1$ and $k2$, and let $u1$ and $u2$ be the corresponding partitions that start with $k1$ and $k2$ and with underlying pattern u and v respectively, and use $u1$ and $u2$ as input for *OVERLAP*. For example, *OVERLAP1*($[1, 1, 0], [0, 0, 1], 4, 2$) corresponds to *OVERLAP*($[4, 3, 2, 2], [2, 2, 2, 1]$), and also outputs $\{[q^7, 2], [q^9, 1]\}$.

Now we are ready to compute $w(C(A, v, k, l, w))$:

$$w(C(A, v, k, l, w)) = (-1)q^{sum\{v,k\}}(\text{if } k = l + sum(v) \text{ and } w = |v| + 1) - \sum_{k1=1}^k \sum_{u \in A} \sum_{p \in OVERLAP1(v,u,k,k1)} p[1] \cdot w(C(A, u, k1, l, w - |v| - 1 + p[2])).$$

Note: in the formula above, $\{v, k\}$ denotes the partition that starts with k and has underlying pattern v , for example, $\{0, 1, 4\} = [4, 4, 3]$; $|v|$ is the length of the pattern v ; $p[1]$ denotes the first part of the list p and $p[2]$ denotes the second part of p .

In this formula, the part before the minus sign corresponds to the first scenario, where the cluster has only one mark, and we will leave it to the reader to verify. If we are in the second scenario (computing the weight of the clusters that have more than one mark), we choose a pattern u from A , a largest part $k1$ ($1 \leq k1 \leq k$), and $\{u, k1\}$ is chosen to be the second mark of the cluster. We need to find all the ways $\{u, k1\}$ can overlap with $\{v, k\}$ (that is, compute *OVERLAP1*($v, u, k, k1$)). Let us use the previous example $\{v, k\} = \{[1, 1, 0], 4\} = [4, 3, 2, 2]$, $\{u, k1\} = \{[0, 0, 1], 2\} = [2, 2, 2, 1]$. There are two ways they can overlap, if the overlap is $[2, 2]$, then $p[1]$ would be q^7 , and $p[2]$ would be 2. After chopping off the $[4, 3]$ (that is, chopping off the first mark, leaving the overlapping part $[2, 2]$), we would get a smaller cluster that starts with $k1 = 2$, still ends with l , and with width $(w - |v| - 1 + p[2])$, thus the formula above.

Remark. One may wonder why we have to include the width as a variable. If we do not, and if $[0]$ or $[0, 0]$, or $[0, 0, 0]$ etc. is in A , then we would have infinitely many clusters (suppose there exist at least one cluster, we can then insert as many marks as we wanted in the middle) and we would have an infinite loop in our program.

3. The ‘Positive’ Approach

While, for enumerating words (in a fixed alphabet) avoiding a given set of ‘patterns’ (occurrences of consecutive subwords), the negative approach, pioneered by Goulden and Jackson [3], is (usually) more efficient, it turns out that this is not the case for the present problem of counting partitions avoiding the kind of patterns discussed here.

The ‘positive’ approach, to be described in this section, turns out to be much more efficient than the negative approach described in the previous section. Nevertheless, we believe that this partition analog of the Goulden–Jackson method is very elegant and has theoretical interest. It is also possible that it may lead to more efficient approaches.

We use an extension of the dynamical programming approach described in the introduction that gave a quadratic-time and quadratic memory algorithm to compute the original partition sequence $\{p(n)\}$, the iconic OEIS sequence A41.

It relied on the obvious fact that removing the largest part, λ_1 , from a partition $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k)$, results in a smaller partition, $\lambda = (\lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k)$, without extra conditions, except that $\lambda_2 \leq \lambda_1$. That is why, in the dynamical programming approach described in the introduction, we were forced to compute the more refined quantity, with two arguments, $P(n, m)$, and that set up the recurrence scheme rolling.

If the set of forbidden patterns, A , consists only of patterns of length 1,

$$A = \{[a_1], [a_2], \dots, [a_k]\},$$

then the analog of (*Fundamental Recurrence*) is easy. Let $p_A(n)$ be the number of partitions of n that avoid the patterns in the set A , and let $P_A(n, m)$ be the number of such partitions whose largest part is m . Then

$$P_A(n, m) = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq m' \leq m \\ m-m' \notin \{a_1, \dots, a_k\}}} P_A(n-m, m'), \quad n \geq m \geq 1,$$

and $p_A(n) = \sum_{m=1}^n P_A(n, m)$.

In order to motivate the general case, let us first do a simple special case, where we want to avoid the single pattern $[1, 1, 1]$. In other words, the set of patterns that we want to avoid is the singleton set $A = \{[1, 1, 1]\}$. Consider a typical such partition $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k)$, whose largest part, λ_1 , is m . If $\lambda_2 \neq \lambda_1 - 1$, then removing λ_1 results in the same type of partition, hence the number of partitions of n that we are interested in, with $\lambda_1 = m$ and $\lambda_2 = m'$, is exactly the same as the number of such partitions of $n - m$ with largest part λ_2 , since there is a one-to-one correspondence. If we have a good partition of $n - m$ with largest part m' , then sticking m in the front cannot cause trouble, since $m - m' \neq 1$, so the forbidden pattern $[1, 1, 1]$ cannot emerge.

On the other hand, if $m' = m - 1$ then we can create new trouble. If we have a partition of n , the form

$$(m, m - 1, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_k),$$

then the ‘be-headed’ partition of $n - m$

$$(m - 1, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_k),$$

must, in addition to avoiding the pattern $[1, 1, 1]$, also avoid the pattern $[1, 1]$ at the start. This forces us to introduce a new quantity, let us call it $P'_{[1,1,1]}(n, m)$, the number of partitions of n with largest part m , avoiding the pattern $[1, 1, 1]$ everywhere and, in addition, avoiding the pattern $[1, 1]$ at the very beginning:

$$P_{[1,1,1]}(n, m) = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq m' \leq m \\ m' \neq m-1}} P_{[1,1,1]}(n - m, m') + P'_{[1,1,1]}(n - m, m - 1).$$

We now need to set up a scheme for $P'_{[1,1,1]}(n, m)$. If we have a partition of n whose largest part is m , avoiding $[1, 1, 1]$ and, in addition avoiding $[1, 1]$ at the beginning and has the second largest part m' with $m - m' \neq 1$, then removing the largest part, m , results in a partition of $n - m$ avoiding the pattern $[1, 1, 1]$ and has no conditions at the beginning. On the other hand, if $m' = m - 1$, then we have a partition of $n - m$ with largest part $m - 1$, avoiding $[1, 1, 1]$ and, in addition, avoiding the pattern $[1]$ at the beginning. Let $P''_{[1,1,1]}(n, m)$ be the number of such partitions. We have

$$P'_{[1,1,1]}(n, m) = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq m' \leq m \\ m' \neq m-1}} P_{[1,1,1]}(n - m, m') + P''_{[1,1,1]}(n - m, m - 1).$$

Similarly,

$$P''_{[1,1,1]}(n, m) = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq m' \leq m \\ m' \neq m-1}} P_{[1,1,1]}(n - m, m') + P'''_{[1,1,1]}(n - m, m - 1),$$

where $P'''_{[1,1,1]}(n, m)$ is the number of partitions of n with largest part m avoiding the pattern $[1, 1, 1]$ and, in addition, avoiding the empty list, $[\]$, at the beginning. But this can never happen so $P'''_{[1,1,1]}(n, m)$ is always zero. Note that we were forced to introduce two auxiliary quantities, $P'(n, m)$ and $P''(n, m)$, that arose naturally.

In general, for any given set of patterns A , the computer automatically sets up a scheme, introducing more general quantities, parameterized, in addition to the set of *global* conditions A , by a set of *local* conditions that should be avoided at the very beginning. Then, for each such set of beginning restrictions, A' , depending on m' , either we are back to only the global conditions, A , i.e., the new A' is the empty set, or if $m - m'$ happens to be one of the starting entries of A or A' , the chopped partition, of $n - m$, in addition to obeying the global restrictions of A , must obey a brand-new kind of restriction A'' . So each ‘state’ (m, m', A') gives rise to a state (m', m'', A'') for some (possibly empty) set A'' . Finding these ‘children’ states is automatically done by the computer, setting up a quadratic-time scheme. At the end of the day, we are only interested in the case where $A' = \emptyset$, but we are forced to consider these auxiliary quantities. Since there are only finitely many of them

and there are still only two arguments (namely n and m , where $1 \leq m \leq n$), the algorithm remains quadratic time and quadratic memory.

4. Maple Packages

This article is accompanied by two Maple packages, `RPneg.txt` and `RPpos.txt`, implementing the two approaches described above. These are available from the front of the article:

<http://sites.math.rutgers.edu/~zeilberg/mamarim/mamarimhtml/rpr.html>,

where there is a large output file with the first 300 terms of many sequences for many sets of forbidden patterns. Most of them do not seem to be (as yet) in the OEIS, but some are.

The most important procedure in `RPpos.txt` is `xnSeq(N, A)`, that outputs the first N terms in the enumerating sequence for partitions that avoid the set of patterns A .

- For $A = \{[0]\}$, we get, of course, the enumerating sequence for distinct partitions (alias odd partitions) sequence A9 (<http://oeis.org/A000009>).
- For $A = \{[0], [1]\}$, we get the enumerating sequence for partitions whose minimal difference is at least 2 (alias, via Rogers–Ramanujan, into parts 1, 4 modulo 5), sequence A3114 (<http://oeis.org/A003114>).
- For $A = \{[1]\}$, we get the sequence A116931, <http://oeis.org/A116931>, that goes back to MacMahon.

On the other hand, the case $A = \{[2]\}$ is not (yet) in the OEIS.

- For $A = \{[1], [0, 0]\}$, we get the sequence A70047 (<http://oeis.org/A070047>).
- On the other hand, the case $A = \{[2], [0, 0]\}$ is not (yet) in the OEIS.
- The cases $A = \{[0, 0]\}$, $A = \{[0, 0, 0]\}$, $A = \{[0, 0, 0, 0]\}$, correspond to sequences A726, A1935 and A35957 respectively.
- On the other hand, the cases $A = \{[0, 1]\}$, $A = \{[1, 0]\}$ are not there (yet).

5. Future Work

The present algorithms assume that the parts can be anything. It would be fairly straightforward to impose congruence conditions on the parts. A bit more challenging would be to have the restrictions also depend on congruences, for example, Schur’s celebrated 1926 theorem (see [1], p. 116), or the more complicated restrictions featured in Shashank Kanade and Matthew C. Russell’s intriguing conjectures ([4], [5], [6], see also [9], p. 149-152). This is an ongoing project.

6. Conclusion

We addressed the important problem of systematically enumerating classes of integer partitions avoiding any (finite) set of ‘patterns’ (of a natural kind, that includes many classical cases). We presented two algorithms, that we labeled ‘negative’ and ‘positive’. The former is more elegant, while the latter is more efficient.

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